

METHODOLOGICAL AND THEORETICAL APPROACHES TO TEACHING ENGLISH ACROSS AGE GROUPS

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Abstract. In teaching English, it is important to take into account the psychological and cognitive development characteristics of different age groups. This article analysis to identify the most common problems that students face in learning English and to propose effective solutions to them. These solutions include interactive teaching methods, the use of technological tools, increasing student motivation, and focusing on cultural context. These approaches are essential for achieving effective results in English language teaching.

Key words: teaching English, approaches, methods, school learners, children, age groups, education, experience, learning a language

Аннотация. При обучении английскому языку важно учитывать особенности психологического и когнитивного развития разных возрастных групп. Анализ данной статьи позволит выявить наиболее распространенные проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются студенты при изучении английского языка, и предложить эффективные решения для них. Эти решения включают интерактивные методы обучения, использование технологических инструментов, повышение мотивации учащихся и сосредоточение внимания на культурном контексте. Эти подходы необходимы для достижения эффективных результатов в преподавании английского языка.

Ключевые слова: преподавание английского языка, подходы, методы, школьники, дети, возрастные группы, образование, опыт, изучение языка.

Annotatsiya. Ingliz tilini o'qitishda turli yosh guruhlarining psixologik va kognitiv rivojlanish xususiyatlarini hisobga olish muhimdir. Ushbu maqola o'quvchilar ingliz tilini o'rganishda duch keladigan eng keng tarqalgan muammolarni aniqlash va ularga samarali yechimlarni taklif qilish uchun tahlil qilinadi. Ushbu yechimlar interaktiv o'qitish usullari, texnologik vositalardan foydalanish, o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasini oshirish va madaniy kontekstga e'tibor qaratishni o'z ichiga oladi. Ushbu yondashuvlar ingliz tilini o'qitishda samarali natijalarga erishish uchun juda muhimdir.

Kalit so'zlar: Ingliz tilini o'qitish, yondashuvlar, usullar, maktab o'quvchilari, bolalar, yosh guruhlari, ta'lim, tajriba, til o'rganish

It is clear that education, like all aspects of our country, is developing from year to year. As a clear result of this, we can cite the opportunities created by our President for young people, including the “Young Book Reader” competition, the “Minister’s Scholarship”, the “Governor’s Scholarship”, and the “Best Foreign Language School”. It is known that the age of language learners is getting younger from year to year. Previously, English was taught from the 5th grade, but now it is taught from kindergarten and later from the 1st grade of school. This, of course, allows pupils to master language skills earlier and faster. As proof of this, it is a joyful situation that various young people from different parts of Uzbekistan are receiving language certificates or achieving the highest scores in the IELTS exams. When it comes to education, language learning, it is advisable to divide this process into several stages, depending on the age limits. Because this approach is correct, taking into account the fact that the stages of human development at different ages are different from each other. Language learners can be divided into four groups:

- Preschool learners (3 - 5 years old)
- Primary school learners (6 - 12 years old)
- Higher school learners (13 - 17 years old)
- Adult learners (18+ years old).

Particularly, increasing student motivation, using interactive methods, and utilizing modern technologies are seen as solutions to these problems. Understanding cultural differences is an important aspect of language learning, which has a significant impact on students' successful language acquisition. The topic of problems and solutions in English language teaching includes research aimed at improving the effectiveness of the educational process, teaching students to communicate in English, and overcoming difficulties in learning the language. The main problems in English language teaching are analyzed, including difficulties in understanding grammar, pronunciation errors, cultural differences, lack of motivation of students, and ineffective approaches used by teachers.

Preschool children lack motivation to learn new knowledge, their thoughts are scattered, and children at this age are very energetic and playful. At this age, it is very difficult to keep the class calm and keep their attention. That is why, based on some experience, we can say that working with children of kindergarten age can be difficult. Because it is important to constantly play, jump, and sing songs with them. Based on my own experience and research, I can say that preschool children have a more kinesthetic learning style. Because if they dance and sing, for example, if we take the simple songs "Peel banana" and "Head, shoulders, knees and toes", it is enough to repeat these songs two or three times. The child will not forget the song, because he played and performed it, he will remember what he did.

Even at this age, it is a little difficult to focus children's attention on the lesson, since it is natural for them to get bored during lessons, get tired of writing and repeating, so during the lesson, thematic games, breaks, in short, getting the child to stand up and play and give them a rest contribute to the effectiveness of the lesson, albeit a small amount. Games suitable for this age include "Kill the fly", "Who am I?" brainstorming, and working in groups.

In addition to this:

- Using interactive and game-based methods, such as games increasing children's interest in the language, positively contribute to the content of the lesson.
- Using exhibitions: Cards, pictures, real objects, and shapes help to better understand and remember new words.
- Regular routines and repetition: Creating special routines for the lesson and constantly repeating key vocabulary helps to remember the constantly used part of the language.
- Parental support: Involving parents in the learning process is a positive process for language learners. Because not only learning and repetition during the lesson, but also paying attention to learning at home and repeating the learned information in the form of questions and answers increases the quality of the child's learning.

Upper-class pupils have different aspects from the two groups of pupils listed above. The reason is that it takes a little more effort to impress and interest upper-class pupils in the lesson. At this age, not all pupils are interested in learning a language because they are interested in the lesson and the language; some are interested, while others may study it because it is a mandatory subject at school. Therefore, it is natural that the level of language proficiency of pupils at this age is also different. This requires teachers to take an individual approach to each pupil. For example, you can choose a field that interests them (for example, cinema, cartoons, famous people, politics, sports) and interest them in this way. Because it is a much better way to interest children in learning a language through topics that are interesting and understandable to them. Similarly, social networks (grammar video lessons on YouTube, videos on Tiktok can also be used as exercises to improve speaking skills" But there are also advantages to teaching a language at this age. At this age, pupils are more organized, which makes it much easier to explain the lesson. There are also no difficulties in dividing pupils into groups. Therefore, every pupil wants to learn and the important thing is the correct approach.

Adult language learners are very different from those listed above. "Because their language learning needs are purposeful. For example, some are for entering higher education institutions, others for going abroad, others for traveling, etc. Usually, older learners come with a lot of life experience, goals, and different motivations. They can force themselves to learn a language. Therefore, it is

necessary to allow them to correct their own mistakes, considering that it is natural to make mistakes in the language learning process. In addition, giving them the opportunity to express their opinions through real-life examples, discussions, cases, and try to solve problems will motivate them even more. Choosing materials that suit the interests and goals of each learner also allows them to improve their language skills. Learners of this age want to be respected. Therefore, it is important to check whether the information being taught is appropriate for their age. For example, online articles, menus, maps, didactic, life or comic videos on YouTube, and The use of podcasts is much more effective. In conclusion, we can say that language teaching at different ages differs from each other. The use of different didactic and scientific materials for learners of different ages gives effective results. In the process of organizing various interactive games, creating dialogues, and using role-play methods during the lesson, learners develop the ability to apply grammatical rules correctly. Despite the fact that children in kindergarten and younger years have a high interest in learning languages, learners of any age can study with such motivation and demonstrate excellent speaking skills in a foreign language.

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